

MEASURING TENSILE STRENGTH OF NANOFIBRES USING A NANOMANIPULATOR INSIDE A SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

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SUMMARY

Mechanical characterization of nanofibres may be the first step to investigate any possibility of developing nanofibre reinforced composites. Since conventional test methods are inadequate for this purpose, a new method that can measure the tensile behaviour of nanofibres including their tensile strength was developed using a nanomanipulator inside a scanning electron microscope (SEM). An axiom that as nanofibres become thinner their tensile strength increases is validated using the developed method. Finally, a feasibility of developing advanced composites using nanofibres will be discussed at the Conference.

Keywords: Nanofibres, Mechanical properties, Nano tensile test, Nanomanipulator

INTRODUCTION

Nanofibres have been used in various applications such as scaffolds in biomimetic engineering [1], filter media in membrane science [2], sensors for gas detection [3], and reinforcements for nanocomposite fabrication [4] because they may have superior mechanical properties. In order to extend the application of nanofibres to structural materials, the measurement of mechanical properties of a single nanofibre is strongly required. However, the conventional tensile testing methods are inappropriate due to the nano-scale nature of the fibres. For the accomplishment of nano tensile test, the challenges such as nano force sensing, nano displacement control, and nano-scaled material observation should be practicable [5].

A tensile test of a carbon nanotube (CNT) performed by Yu et al. [6] using two atomic force microscope (AFM) cantilevers inside a SEM may not be applied to the other nanomaterials such as polymeric nanofibres because nanofibres are easily melted by electron-beam-induced deposition (EBID). Tan et al. [7] conducted a tensile test of an electrospun polyethylene oxide (PEO) nanofibre using an AFM cantilever and inverted microscope stage under CCD camera observation, but this test method is limited to the fibres with an observable diameter of the CCD camera. Similarly, Zussman et al. [8] performed a tensile test of a nylon-6,6 nanofibre using an AFM cantilever and stainless steel wire under an optical microscopy. However, this test method is also limited to the fibres with an observable diameter of the microscope.

In this work a new method that can measure tensile strength of nanofibres is presented. This method consists of a SEM, nanomanipulator, and AFM cantilever. Nanofibres were electrospun on custom-built Cu substrates which have a gap between substrates, and the nanofibres were uniaxially aligned over the gap. An AFM cantilever and the Cu substrates were mounted on the nanomanipulator to be manipulated. One of the aligned nanofibres was hooked by the AFM cantilever, and the nanofibre was elongated when force is applied to the cantilever until the nanofibre is fractured. The stress is measured from the deflection of AFM cantilever, and the strain is measured from scanning electron microscopy of the nanofibre.

EXPERIMENTAL SCHEME

Specimen Preparation and Electrospinning

Although one piece of conductive collector is used in ordinary electrospinning, two conductive substrates with a gap between the substrates were used to align nanofibres uniaxially over the gap. In this work 10 wt% polyethylene terephthalate (PET) nanofibres were electrospun on Cu substrates which have 2mm gap between the substrates. The electrospun PET fibres were uniaxially aligned over the conductive substrates, placed on an insulating substrate, by electrostatic attraction and repulsion [9, 10]. Tiny insulators such as a small piece of Teflon film were placed between the Cu substrates to electrically separate the two Cu substrates. The two Cu substrates were electrically grounded to send surplus electrons away. Since many numbers of entangled nanofibres may interrupt the movement of AFM cantilever during elongation process of the nanofibre, electrospinning in short time less than 1 second is strongly preferred. The electrospun fibres on Cu substrates were fixed by conductive silver paste, which is compatible in a SEM chamber, to avoid slippage when the force is applied. Figure 1 depicts the process of specimen preparation and entire electrospinning setup.

Figure 1. Schematic electrospinning setup with two Cu substrates

Nanomanipulator Assembly

A nanofibre cannot be observed readily through optical microscopy since an optical microscope has insufficient resolution and depth of field. Therefore, SEM was employed for the observation of nanofibres. For the nano displacement control the nanomanipulator is operated in a SEM chamber. The compact nanomanipulator consists of X, Y, Z stages (Sigma Koki, TSDS-252S, 253) assembled on Al base plate to achieve three-axis linear motions as shown in Figure 2. The nanomanipulator accomplished three linear degrees of freedom. The stages were made of stainless steel to resist in vacuum condition during real time observation in a SEM chamber, and vacuum compatible silicone lubricant was used between the stage bearings for out-gassing protection during the stage movement [11].

Piezoelectric actuators (New Focus, 8353-V), which achieved 30nm minimal incremental motion, were connected into the stages, and each actuator controls the linear movement of each stage. The actuators are also vacuum compatible up to 10^{-6} Torr to be operated in the SEM chamber [12]. Since the actuators are practicable to be operated in nanometre scale, they are feasible to manipulate nanomaterials including nanofibres.

The AFM cantilever was mounted on X, Y stages for the nano force sensing, and the platinum-coated cantilever was selected for clear observation during nanomanipulation. On the other hand, the Cu substrate was mounted on Z stages. X, Y stages and Z stage were separated each other to have minimum height to protect the contact between the nanomanipulator and SEM components. Among many commercial X, Y, Z stages and actuators the minimum sized models were selected and assembled to reduce the total dimensions of nanomanipulator. Also, minimum number of stages and actuators were employed. The dimension of the nanomanipulator is approximately 70mm × 50mm × 30 mm (width, length, height). The nanomanipulator is much compact and simple compared to other nanomanipulators [13-15], but can versatilely control the nanofibres in three linear degrees of freedom. In this work JEOL JSM-6390LV SEM was used since the SEM has sufficient chamber space. Lower accelerating voltage during real time observation is preferred to avoid the fibre damage.

The Teflon-coated electrical wires from the actuators were connected to a control driver via custom-built vacuum feedthrough so that the nanomanipulator inside the chamber can be controlled by the control driver outside the chamber. Figure 2 demonstrates the 3D-CAD schematics of nanomanipulator inside a SEM chamber. For clear demonstration the dimensions of cantilever and nanofibre were exaggerated, and electrical wires were omitted.

Figure 2. 3D-CAD schematics of nanomanipulator in a SEM chamber

Elongation Process of a Nanofibre and Stress and Strain Measurement

When the stainless steel stages are manipulated by the piezo actuators, the mounted AFM cantilever is manipulated as well. The AFM cantilever is approached to the centre of the aligned nanofibre between fixed points in order to hook the nanofibre (Figure 3). While the cantilever is manipulated forward, the nanofibre is elongated. Consequently, the cantilever is deflected as the cone-shaped AFM tip secures the hooking between the nanofibre and cantilever by the tip's intrinsic geometry. The nanofibre is continuously elongated until the nanofibre is fractured.

Figure 3. Elongation process of a nanofibre by AFM cantilever

Applied force to the nanofibre can be measured from the deflection of AFM cantilever as shown in Figure 4. Therefore, the selection of AFM cantilever with the proper force constant is significant for the clear observation of deflection. The AFM cantilever (Mikromasch, NSC19/Ti-Pt) used here has specific force constant (0.6 N/m) which is measured by the analysis of oscillation damping in liquid [16]. The degree of cantilever deflection is determined in scanning electron microscopy considering the tilt angle of the nanomanipulator in the chamber. Then, the applied force is calculated based on the force constant and cantilever deflection. Finally, the stress is calculated from the applied force and the cross-sectional area of the nanofibre.

To measure the strain of the fibre, scanning electron microscopy considering the tilt angle of the nanomanipulator is also required. Since the fibre is suspended over the substrates and fixed by the silver paste, the original fibre length is the width of two Cu substrates. The final fibre length is determined from scanning electron microscopy. Then, the elongated length is the difference between the original and final fibre length. Consequently, the strain of the nanofibre can be calculated.

Figure 4. (1) Stress measurement from deflection of an AFM cantilever, and (2) strain measurement from elongation observation of a nanofibre

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nanofibres in the SEM chamber were not coated with conductive materials such as platinum since the coating may change the material properties of the nanofibres. Therefore, the image quality of the non-coated nanofibre was lower than that of the ordinary coated nanofibre. To avoid the fibre damage during the real time observation lower accelerating voltage was preferred, and the lower accelerating voltage may degrade the image resolution and quality. As shown in Figure 5 the PET nanofibre was hooked and elongated by the AFM cantilever. Also, the cantilever deflection was observed. Based on the scanning electron microscopy the stress and the strain can be calculated.

Figure 5. AFM cantilever with the hooked nanofibre: before force applying (left), after force applying (right)

Figure 6 shows the elongation process of the PET nanofibre. As the cantilever was manipulated forward, the nanofibre was elongated. During the elongation process the necking was observed (yellow arrow in Figure 6). Finally, the nanofibre was fractured around the necked area. In this work the cantilever with a cone shaped tip rather than a pyramidal tip was used, so the stress concentration around the tip is somewhat prevented.

Figure 6. Elongation process of the PET nanofibre: during elongation (left), fibre fracture (right)

More experiments will be performed and presented at the Conference. Also, the stress and strain of the nanofibres will be calculated.

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